

Review of India's Financial Inclusion in the Last Decade

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Abstract

Financial inclusion is an important parameter for social inclusion and spells better fiscal development. India has a population of 1.22 billion according to the 2011 census and forty percent of Indians are still "unbanked". Since 1990, after liberalization, the banking sector has taken many ameliorating steps towards growth better economic development in the financial segment and services such as micro-finance institutions, digital money transfer are some of the modes to approach the underserved individuals. But in India, the underprivileged are still skeptical and lack knowledge and awareness of these financial instruments. Even though the RBI has formulated tough measures for financial inclusions the banks need to co-operate more as the situation on the ground provided by the banks does not match the RBI's fervor of inclusion.

Keywords: India; Financial Inclusion

Introduction

Financial inclusion is an important parameter for social inclusion and spells better fiscal development. Globally, it is deemed that the businesses and persons from lower socio-economic strata (read-underprivileged, even disabled) should have access to reasonably priced financial products and services like- savings, insurance, credit, payments, deposits, loans, funds transfer services, etc. It is important as it helps in the inclusive economic growth of the country. In India, since 1990, the banking sector has taken many ameliorating steps towards growth in the financial segment and better economic development (Mehtar, 2014).

The Millenium Development Goals (MDG) have given importance to eradicating poverty and this can be attained via the financial services and products tailored to the needs of the poor and underprivileged population. Financial inclusion is an intermediation approach to overcome the market friction that does not help the underprivileged and this can be achieved by availing financial services at the right place, form, price, and time (Aduda and Kalunda, 2012).

Social exclusion is rampant amongst impoverished people and differs culturally and geographically. Moreover, such individuals are more prone to be skeptical when offered financial services and this can be a deterrent for the economy as the poor get poorer as compared to the rich (Aduda and Kalunda, 2012).

Hanning and Jansen (2010), have further explained this notion that there should be policies for the "unbanked" populace who should have the opportunity towards the contribution of finance, equity, growth, and economic development to alleviate poverty. India has a population of 1.22 billion according to the 2011 census and forty percent of Indians are still "unbanked".

Banks are the most important financial institutions of India and the number of bank branches in the urban areas outnumbers the ones in rural areas by 3.5 to 0.6 respectively (Meher, 2014). Uttar Pradesh and Maharashtra have the highest number of bank branches and Bihar has the lowest number. Foreign and private sector banks are mostly located in the metropolitan cities and only thirty percent of the banks have a branch in the rural areas.

Therefore this review is going to look into the status of various financial services and methods of financial inclusion in India since the last decade in the form of planning the product, it's processing, and preparing the staff to deliver tailored products and services, among the low socio-economic sections of society.

Literature Review

Indian banks have witnessed two landmark scenarios based on the following parameters of location and lending process of the banks - one in 1969, which was the nationalization of the banks i.e. for every one urban branch the bank had to start four in the rural unbanked areas. The reason for the failure of nationalized banks strategy towards financial inclusion was that they concentrated only on providing credit and their priority targets were for mostly MSME(Micro Small Medium-sized enterprises) and did not do much for encouraging savings or building a deposit scheme or encompassing the payment system (Barua et al., 2016). The other strategy was liberalization in the 1990s which broke the above policy. Liberalization was the start of financial services such as micro-finance banks, digital money transfer are some of the modes to approach the underserved individuals. The banking program after 1990 has moved towards social programs especially in agriculture and small-scale industries to the underserved populace (Mehtar, 2014).

In 2005, RBI (Reserve Bank of India) gave an operational definition to Financial Inclusion and urged the banks to increase the lending to the weaker sections by twenty-five percent (Mehtar, 2014).

Time line of RBI's Guidelines for Financial Inclusion (as mentioned by Mehtar, 2014 and Barua et al., 2016)

2005	Term Financial Inclusion was coined in their annual report
2005-6	Asked the banks to support the Financial Inclusion criteria
2008	Mobile Banking- mobile wallets
2009	FLCC(Financial literacy and credit counselling “ <i>One District, One Bank Model</i> ”
2010-11	Swabhiman Campaign- banks instructed to open branches in the unbanked populace of five thousand and more occupancies
2011	RBI regulates MFI's with Industry code of conduct
2013	RBI launched a financial literacy project
2015	Payment banks (11) and small finance banks(10) to allow current and savings accounts upto one lakh per customer with ATM's and business correspondents like Bank Mitra's

According to Barua et al (2016), India has witnessed an overall increase in the following services from 2005- 2013: ATM's (per 100,000 individuals) has increased from 2.3 to 13.3; commercial bank branches (per 1000 km) 23.2 to 3.7; Deposit accounts with commercial bank branches (per 1000 individuals) from 611 to 1197.60; Loan accounts with commercial bank branches (per 1000 individuals) from 101 to 147 (Barua et al., 2016). Post offices in India also provide services such as insurance, saving structures, cash certificates, money orders, pension products, mutual funds, etc. (Barua et al., 2016).

India has taken large strides in the direction of the deposit account sector as the government's initiative towards MNREGA(2009), a national employment guarantee scheme i.e. deposition of money directly to the worker in their bank account has increased transparency and boosted the banking services. Under the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), 190 million accounts were operational by October 2015, with credit and debit cards and overdraft facility after six months of opening the account and very low minimum balance. But still, it was observed that the MNREGA account holders just withdrew money from the account and did not use any other financial services(Barua et al., 2016).

In 2016 the Mor Committee on Comprehensive Financial Services for Small Businesses and Low-Income Households proposed that all individuals above the age of 18 years should have a fully serviceable bank account with credit, investment, deposit, insurance products available to them as their legal right. RBI then occasioned the banks to open 80,000 additional branches in the rural areas but only 7,459 were started and that too operated only deposit and payment facilities the other products were not offered in the rural branches(Barua et al., 2016).

Furthermore, small banks were created in rural areas, but they too did not meet with much success as the major concern of financial inclusion is financial stability, as in the current economic scenario especially in the fragmented markets giving rise to lose in the form of market failure and to bring about financial inclusion it should be beneficial to both the provider and the beneficiary(Aduda and Kalunda, 2012). In India, the underprivileged populace is not considered to be the market that the banks want to cater to and

they are not happy serving them as the cost of small transactions, low-profit margins, inability to provide collateral security (Barua et al., 2016).

But over the last decade, India has seen an archetype change towards financial services like insurance, entry of specialist banks like micro-finance institutions. The introduction of such strategies can prevent exploitation of the unbanked sector which mostly deals in cash and falls victim to borrowing money at high-interest rates and remaining in their debt forever (Barua et al., 2016).

This matter gave rise to the birth of MFI's(Micro-finance institutions) which are non-profit NGO's that cater to people with new credit methods like small loans to clients through group guarantees and evaluations of cash flow in the households. MFI's in India has grown into successful entities now funded by banks even private and equity of shareholders. Over a period of years, in 2010, some MFI's started coercive debt collection methods and the RBI stepped in in 2011 with directives like better communication of lending rates, loan tenure, repayment methods, customer complaint services, and an Industry Code of Conduct (Barua et al., 2016).

The major issue with financial inclusion is the selection and evaluation of appropriate indicators of measuring the progress of inclusion. For example, the data on financial inclusion must specify the demand and supply of financial services i.e. the use of payment services, insurance products, credit, deposits, remittances to understand the efficacy of the services provided. Qualitative and quantitative surveys must be conducted and the data collected must be benchmarked in comparison to the international level. (Hameedu, 2014)

Conclusion

In the last decade, India has taken a huge responsibility to provide financial products and services to the underprivileged population using technology to provide services like savings, insurance, credit, payments, deposits, loans, fund transfer services, etc.

RBI has upped its initiatives to spread financial inclusion to rural areas by directing the banks to open more branches to rural areas with ATM facility and has restructured the MFI's to conduct businesses responsibly.

But in India, the underprivileged are still skeptical and lack knowledge and awareness of these financial instruments. Even though the RBI has formulated tough measures for financial inclusions, the banks need to co-operate more as the situation on the ground provided by the banks does not match the RBI's fervor of inclusion.

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